

**Thermodynamic Study of Complexation of
Furoin-thiosemicarbazone and Furoin-4-
phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone with
Bivalent Metal Ions**

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*Manuscript received 14 February 1991,
revised 22 August 1991, accepted 20 September 1991*

MUCH work has been done so far in the field of physiological activity of the thiosemicarbazones and their ability to form chelates with metals. But no significant investigation has been made about the properties of the complexes in solution. The present paper deals with the formation constants of binary complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} with

furoin-thiosemicarbazone (F-TSC) and furoin-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (F-4-P-3-TSC) using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO_4) at 30, 40 and 50°.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Ethanol was purified by the standard procedure¹. Double-distilled water was used for preparing the solutions. Standard metal perchlorate solutions were prepared as described earlier². Furoin and its thiosemicarbazones of the ligands (0.01 M) were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of the compound in ethanol.

An Elico LT-120 digital pH meter equipped with combination electrode was used. The readings of pH meter in 50% ethanol-water were corrected for solvent effect as previously reported³. pH-metric titrations were carried out as described earlier². In order to determine the thermodynamic parameters, the titrations were carried out at temperatures 30, 40 and 50° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Procedure : The following three solutions (total volume 40 ml in each case) were titrated against

standard sodium hydroxide solution (0.98 M): (i) 4 ml 0.2 M HClO_4 + 0.78 ml 4 M NaClO_4 + 20 ml ethanol + 15.22 ml distilled water, (ii) 4 ml 0.2 M HClO_4 + 0.78 ml 4 M NaClO_4 + 20 ml 0.01 M reagent + 15.22 ml distilled water, and (iii) 2 ml 0.2 M HClO_4 + 2 ml 0.02 M metal perchlorate solution containing 0.2 M HClO_4 + 0.77 ml 4 M NaClO_4 + 20 ml 0.01 M reagent + 15.23 ml distilled water.

Results and Discussion

F-TSC and F-4-P-3-TSC ligands undergo first deprotonation in the thiol group forming mono-deprotonated species. Ligands are therefore likely to be monobasic and bidentate with sulphur and hydrazinic nitrogen as the donor atoms⁶. The probable complexation equilibria may be written as,

The proton-ligand and the metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁷. From the titration data \bar{n}_A values were calculated and plotted against pH to obtain pK values. These were further corroborated by linear plots of $\bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs pH. F-TSC and F-4-P-3-TSC have only one dissociable proton from SH group, and the second proton from OH group is not easily dissociable as the formation curves extend over the range of \bar{n}_A values >0.1 to ≈ 1 . The pK values for F-4-P-3-TSC was found higher than F-TSC due to presence of benzene ring in the chain. The results are accurate within ± 0.02 .

From the metal titration curves \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation

TABLE I

Ligand	Cation	Stability constant	β at Temp.			$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (J mol ⁻¹)
			30°	40°	50°	30°	30°	30°
F-TSC	H ⁺	log K_1^H	11.77	11.52	11.31	67.81	45.08	-75.01
		log K_2	11.30	10.51	10.24	65.11	142.47	255.31
	Cu ^{II}	log K_1	10.09	9.96	9.70	61.59	131.65	231.20
		log K_2	10.11	9.49	9.32	58.25	111.81	176.70
	Ni ^{II}	log K_1	9.34	8.58	8.33	53.81	137.06	274.73
		log K_2	9.67	9.06	8.66	55.71	110.00	179.18
	Co ^{II}	log K_1	8.71	8.07	7.65	50.18	115.42	215.29
		log K_2	8.95	8.15	7.69	51.57	144.27	305.95
	Zn ^{II}	log K_1	7.93	7.26	6.84	45.69	120.82	247.97
		log K_2	8.04	7.43	7.03	46.32	110.00	210.17
	Mn ^{II}	log K_1	7.19	6.50	6.20	41.43	124.43	273.95
		log K_2						
F-4-P-3-TSC	H ⁺	log K_1^H	11.97	11.71	11.40	68.97	46.89	-72.87
		log K_2	11.09	10.82	10.45	63.90	48.69	50.18
	Cu ^{II}	log K_1	10.16	9.71	9.34	58.54	81.15	74.63
		log K_2	10.73	9.94	9.54	61.82	142.47	266.15
	Ni ^{II}	log K_1	9.44	8.77	8.34	54.39	120.82	219.26
		log K_2	10.22	9.34	8.74	58.88	158.70	329.48
	Co ^{II}	log K_1	8.86	8.22	7.68	51.05	115.41	212.43
		log K_2	9.12	8.57	8.21	52.55	99.18	153.93
	Zn ^{II}	log K_1	8.07	7.50	6.90	46.50	102.79	185.79
		log K_2	8.47	7.75	7.32	48.80	129.84	267.46
	Mn ^{II}	log K_1	7.43	6.72	6.30	42.81	128.04	281.29
		log K_2						

curves of the metal complexes and the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were evaluated therefrom. They were further corroborated by linear plots of $\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})$ vs pL and $\log (2-\bar{n})/(\bar{n}-1)$ vs pL. The values of $\log K$ are accurate within ± 0.03 log units. The stability constant data and the thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° are summarised in Table 1.

The order of stability constants in the metal complexes of F-TSC and F-4-P-3-TSC has been found to be, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, which is in good agreement with the order found by Irving and Williams. The $\log K$ values of the complexes were plotted against the ionic radii, electronegativity and ionisation potentials of the metal ions. The formation constants were found to increase with the increase in the above periodic properties but decrease with increase in temperature.

The ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° values accompanying the metal-ligand complexation reaction were calculated at 30° using well-known relations⁹. The data (Table 1) show negative ΔG° values indicating spontaneous reactions. The ΔS° values are all positive indicating that the change in entropy favours complex formation. Further, negative values of ΔH° predicts the exothermic nature of the complex reactions and strong metal-sulphur bond¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.S.R.) is thankful to Prof. N. N. Maldar for his keen interest, Prof. D. V. Jahagirdar for constant encouragement and Dr. S. V. Lonikar for help in preparing the manuscript.

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